

1 **Piezoelectric In Situ Stress Measurement in a Large-Volume Press and Deformation**
2 **Experiments on MgO and Forsterite Single Crystals**

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8 **Key Points:**

- 9
- 10 • A six-ram press is used to perform deformation experiments at high pressures and temperatures on single crystal samples.
 - 11 • A piezoelectric crystal with the sample column of the experiments is used to estimate the stress in situ.
 - 12
 - 13 • Stress strain results agree with established creep laws matching earlier single crystal magnesium oxide and forsterite data
 - 14
 - 15

16 **Abstract**

17 Accurate stress measurement remains a central challenge in high-pressure deformation
18 experiments on mantle minerals at pressures >2 GPa. In most large-volume press studies, stress
19 is inferred indirectly from in situ synchrotron X-ray diffraction by converting azimuthal lattice-
20 strain variations into differential stress, restricting experiments to specialized beamline
21 facilities. We present a piezoelectric method for direct stress measurement in an independently
22 acting six-ram multianvil press. A calcium tantalate gallium silicate (CTGS) crystal embedded in
23 the deformation column of a cubic high-pressure assembly generates electrical charge
24 proportional to deviatoric stress. The crystal is displaced toward the cool end of the assembly
25 while the sample remains centered in the furnace, preserving mechanical coupling while
26 minimizing thermally induced charge leakage at the crystal. The signal is recorded continuously
27 using a precision charge integrator and corrected for temperature-dependent drift with a
28 constrained parabolic model. Thermal calibration demonstrates that the crystal remains below
29 ~ 200 °C, while the sample can be deformed at temperatures up to 1400 °C. After propagating
30 uncertainties in capacitance, electrode geometry, and piezoelectric response, the stress noise
31 level is ~ 2 MPa with a conservative detection threshold near 5 MPa. The method is validated
32 using single-crystal deformation experiments on MgO and forsterite at 1.5–3 GPa and 600–
33 1300 °C. Stress–strain curves reproduce expected pressure strengthening, thermal weakening,
34 and transitions to steady-state creep. Fitted creep parameters agree with established
35 synchrotron-based datasets, demonstrating that piezoelectric sensing provides reliable in situ
36 stress histories and enables high-throughput laboratory deformation experiments on mantle
37 minerals.

38 **Plain Language Summary**

39 Understanding how rocks and minerals deform deep inside Earth is essential for explaining
40 processes such as plate tectonics, earthquakes, and mantle flow. Reproducing these
41 environments requires devices that reproduce high pressures and temperatures but measuring
42 stresses- i.e. the forces acting inside a deforming rock- under such conditions is difficult.
43 Current methods often depend on specialized synchrotron X-ray facilities that have limited
44 access. We introduce a new way to measure stress in a large high-pressure device using a
45 piezoelectric crystal. When squeezed, the crystal produces an electric charge that directly
46 reflects the applied stress. Our design keeps the crystal relatively cool (below about 200 °C)
47 while the rock sample can be deformed at temperatures up to 1400 °C, which prevents
48 temperature-induced leakage of the piezoelectric charge. We also developed electronics that
49 correct small electrical drift caused by heating, ensuring stable long-duration measurements.
50 Experiments on single crystals of magnesia (MgO) and forsterite under mantle conditions show
51 that the method reproduces established laboratory results. Because this approach does not
52 require access to large synchrotron facilities, it allows more frequent and lower-cost
53 experiments on how rocks deform at depth. This method expands our ability to study the

54 mechanical behavior of Earth's interior and improves constraints on the processes that drive
55 tectonics and volcanism.

56

57 **1 Introduction**

58 Understanding the mechanical behavior of Earth's mantle requires laboratory measurements
59 that constrain the creep properties of minerals under high-pressure and high-temperature
60 conditions. These experiments depend on accurate determinations of stress and strain rate,
61 from which mineral flow laws are derived. At pressures less than 0.5 GPa, stresses can be
62 measured with high precision using the Paterson apparatus, where the confining pressure is
63 transmitted hydrostatically through a gas medium and load is monitored directly. While piston–
64 cylinder–based solid-medium devices such as the Griggs apparatus extend this range to
65 approximately 2 GPa, stress resolution decreases as confining pressure increases. At higher
66 pressures relevant to the deeper upper mantle, multi-anvil presses can in principle reproduce
67 the required pressure-temperature conditions (Wang et al., 2003; Manthilake et al., 2012), but
68 accurate stress determination becomes significantly more difficult.

69 In most such experiments, stress is measured using in situ synchrotron X-ray diffraction.
70 Azimuthal variations in lattice spacing around Debye–Scherrer rings record elastic strain in the
71 sample, which is converted to differential stress using known elastic constants, potentially
72 coupled to micromechanical models (Burnley & Zhang, 2008; Mei et al., 2010; Burnley, 2015).
73 For experiments on aligned single-crystals, where Debye–Scherrer rings are not produced,
74 stress must instead be inferred from an adjacent polycrystalline calibrant (Girard et al., 2012;
75 Girard et al., 2013).

76 While this approach has enabled major advances in high-pressure rheology, it has important
77 limitations. Experiments must be performed at synchrotron radiation facilities where user
78 access is limited, which restricts the number and duration of experiments that can be
79 performed. In addition, uncertainties associated with diffraction geometry and lattice d-spacing
80 determination typically limit precision and favor conditions where relatively large stresses
81 develop. These constraints make routine, high-accuracy stress determination at mantle
82 pressures and temperatures challenging and motivate the development of alternative
83 approaches that operate independently of synchrotron diffraction.

84 Piezoelectric materials provide a potential route to such measurements because they generate
85 electrical charge in response to applied mechanical stress. If a piezoelectric sensor can be
86 embedded in a high-pressure assembly and thermally protected from the furnace, it can
87 function as an in-situ stress gauge during deformation. To date, however, the mechanical
88 response of piezoelectric materials at pressures and temperatures achievable in multi-anvil
89 presses has not been investigated.

90 Here we develop and test a piezoelectric method for direct stress measurement in a cubic
91 large-volume press. A calcium tantalate gallium silicate (CTGS) crystal is placed within the
92 deformation column of a high-pressure assembly and generates a charge proportional to
93 deviatoric stress, which is recorded continuously using a precision charge integrator. We

94 characterize temperature-dependent electrical leakage, implement a drift-correction scheme,
95 and quantify the measurement precision. We then validate the approach using deformation
96 experiments on single-crystal MgO and forsterite at upper mantle pressures and temperatures.
97 Agreement with established creep behavior demonstrates that piezoelectric sensing provides
98 accurate in situ stress histories in solid-media presses and offers a promising practical route to
99 expanded experimental constraints on mantle rheology.

100 **2 Materials and Methods**

101 2.1 Piezoelectric crystal

102 Piezoelectric materials generate electrical charge proportional to applied mechanical stress and
103 are widely used as force and pressure sensors. The relation between the measured charge, Q ,
104 and the applied stress σ can be written as,

$$105 \quad \sigma = \frac{Q}{d_{ijk}A} \quad [1]$$

106 where d_{ijk} is the piezoelectric coefficient and A is the surface area of the crystal. The suitability
107 of a piezoelectric sensor for high-pressure deformation experiments depends not only on the
108 magnitude of d_{ijk} , but also on the thermodynamic and electrical stability at elevated
109 temperatures and pressures. Temperature-dependent electrical conduction can produce charge
110 leakage through and around the crystal that obscures the mechanical signal (Poplavko, 2019;
111 Rofifah, 2020), making long-duration measurements particularly challenging. A practical
112 piezoelectric stress gauge must therefore combine mechanical robustness with high resistivity
113 and thermodynamic stability under experimental conditions. This not only makes demands on
114 the choice of crystal but means that the temperature at the crystal should remain as low as
115 possible and the material around the crystal needs to maintain a high electrical resistance.

116 Quartz (α -quartz) was initially tested because of its well-characterized piezoelectric properties
117 ($d_{11}=2.31$ pC/N; Kochin et al., 2004), but it is unsuitable for high-temperature deformation
118 experiments. Above 573 °C, α -quartz transforms to β -quartz, where the relevant piezoelectric
119 coefficient vanishes (Dolino & Bachheimer, 1982). In addition, α -quartz is prone to Dauphiné
120 twinning through ferroelastic switching, which reverses the sign of the piezoelectric response
121 and corrupts stress estimates (Guzzo & Boy, 2000; Shiao et al., 1984). The coercive stress
122 required for such switching decreases rapidly with temperature and falls below ~ 100 MPa by
123 200 °C, (Shiao et al., 1984) making reliable measurements at elevated temperature impractical.

124 Instead, calcium tantalate gallium silicate was selected (CTGS, $\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$), which is a
125 langasite-type crystal with the same trigonal symmetry as α -quartz but with greater thermal
126 and electrical stability (Z. Wang et al., 2003; Yu et al., 2011; Ma et al., 2017; Suhak et al., 2018;
127 Ouyang et al., 2021). CTGS exhibits no phase transitions up to its melting range (~ 1400 – 1750 K),
128 and reports of ferroelastic twinning are absent despite symmetry allowing it, indicating low
129 susceptibility in practice. Its higher piezoelectric coefficient (4.0 pC/N) and greater electrical

130 resistivity further improve signal quality. These attributes make CTGS well suited for in situ
131 stress sensing in multi-anvil deformation experiments.

132 2.2 Assembly Design

133 High pressure and temperature deformation experiments were performed on single crystals of
134 periclase and forsterite using a cubic multi-anvil large-volume press equipped with six
135 independently controlled hydraulic rams (Manthilake et al., 2012). A 15 mm edge-length
136 truncated Cr₂O₃-doped MgO cubic assembly was used with 10 mm square faceted WC anvils.
137 The hydrostatic pressure calibration follows Sano-Furukawa et al. (2014). Anvil positions are
138 recorded with a precision of 0.1 μm using integrated encoders that provide the strain
139 measurements used in this study.

140 The piezoelectric sensor is an oriented CTGS single-crystal disk (1 mm thick, 4 mm diameter)
141 installed along the deformation axis of the assembly and aligned with the crystallographic a-axis
142 (1-direction), corresponding to the d_{11} piezoelectric coefficient (an X-cut orientation). A 200 nm
143 gold coating is sputtered onto the opposing faces to form electrodes. Sidewall metallization is
144 prevented by masking the crystal edges with cyanoacrylate glue during sputtering; the glue is
145 removed afterward. Copper foils contact the coated faces, and platinum wires woven through
146 the foils serve as electrical leads.

147 The sample is placed asymmetrically towards one end of the sample column, inside an MgO
148 sleeve surrounded by a graphite furnace. The furnace is connected to a top and side anvil using
149 molybdenum electrodes. The piezoelectric crystal is displaced to the other end of the sample
150 column and is outside of the furnace and within a single crystal MgO sleeve, to maintain a high
151 electrical resistance. A diamond disk separates the CTGS crystal from the WC anvil and acts as a
152 heat sink to ensure lower temperatures at this end of the sample column. Zirconia fills the
153 space in the sample column between the sample and CTGS crystal. Platinum wires connect to
154 copper electrodes that cover each surface of the CTGS crystal. The wires pass through
155 feedthrough holes within the assembly and are taken out through the pyrophyllite gaskets to
156 the external charge integrator. A full schematic of the assembly and the individual parts, with
157 design, is shown in Supplementary Figures S1–S3 and Table S1.

158 Deformation experiments were performed on synthetically produced single-crystals of MgO
159 and forsterite (Mg₂SiO₄), that were supplied pre-oriented by the manufacturer (Sigma-Aldrich).
160 Cylindrical cores 4 mm in diameter and 4 mm in height were prepared from each crystal. The
161 end faces were polished and aligned to within ±1° to ensure parallel loading. Both crystals were
162 oriented such that the compression axis was parallel to the crystallographic (100) direction.

163 In a typical experiment the pressure is increased to the target hydrostatic value. The assembly
164 is then heated to 1000 °C to relax deviatoric stress accumulated during pressurization. DC
165 furnace power is used to suppress AC electromagnetic interference with the piezoelectric
166 charge measurement. Temperature is subsequently ramped to the deformation setpoint at 25
167 °C min⁻¹, and the piezoelectric voltage is monitored continuously. Deformation is performed by
168 advancing the rams in the sample column axis at a controlled displacement rate, while the
169 remaining rams are relaxed. As described in the next section, drift determinations are made
170 before and after deformation.

171 To avoid complexities in the thermal and stress regime no thermocouple is placed in the
172 assembly. A power-to-temperature calibration is established beforehand in experiments that
173 use the same assembly design but substitute the piezoelectric crystal for a type S
174 thermocouple. A second type S thermocouple is placed in the center of the sample area. In the
175 calibration, the assembly was compressed to five different pressures. The results, illustrated in
176 Supplementary Figure S4, confirm that even at a sample temperature of 1200 °C, the
177 temperature over the piezoelectric crystal remains below 200 °C. This temperature gradient
178 ensures the crystal remains cool, which significantly reduces electrical conduction through and
179 around the crystal, that otherwise contributes to drift. The assembly has been used up to a
180 sample temperature of 1400 °C. Beyond this point, the high DC current required for heating
181 begins to melt the molybdenum furnace electrodes at localized hotspots, causing instability and
182 eventual failure. However, maintaining stability at 1400 °C is sufficient for experiments
183 replicating upper mantle conditions.

184 2.3 Charge integrator and drift correction

185 The piezoelectric crystal is connected to a precision integrating transimpedance amplifier
186 (IVC102) that converts stress-induced charge into a measurable voltage. The block diagram for
187 the charge integrator is shown in Supplementary Figure S5. Charge generated by the crystal is
188 accumulated on an external integrating capacitor, $C_F = 9.964$ nF (1% tolerance), so that the
189 output voltage, ΔV , is proportional to the total charge and the applied stress at the piezoelectric
190 crystal, σ_{11} , is,

$$191 \sigma_{11} = \frac{\Delta V \cdot C_F}{d_{11} A} \quad [2]$$

192 where d_{11} is the piezoelectric coefficient and A is the area of the electrode on the crystal. This
193 relation allows direct conversion of the integrator voltage, after drift correction, into deviatoric
194 stress.

195 Finite electrical leakage through the crystal, its housing, cables and front-end circuitry produces
196 a slow background drift in voltage even under constant stress. If the effective resistance
197 changes during an experiment, the slope of this drift changes and the integrator cannot
198 distinguish it from a true piezoelectric signal. We quantified the dependence of drift on
199 resistance using a precision resistance decade (Hochpräzisions-Widerstands-Dekade Typ 1424).
200 The measured relationship is shown in Supplementary Figure S6 with model fitting parameters
201 listed in Supplementary Table S2. Measurements made before and after a deformation
202 experiment indicate a typical starting resistance of ~40 M Ω . Never-the-less, a typical resistance
203 change of 1 M Ω , over a one-hour experiment, produces a drift variation that corresponds to an
204 apparent stress error of ~40 MPa. This sensitivity indicates that maintaining both high and
205 stable resistance across the crystal is essential for accurate stress determination.

206 To account for drift, a post-processing procedure is implemented. Prior to deformation, ~10
207 minutes of baseline data are recorded to characterize the drift and an additional 10 minutes are
208 recorded after deformation to capture the post-strain behavior. Voltage drift is removed by
209 constructing a parabolic function $f(x)$ that interpolates between these measured pre- and post-
210 deformation drift segments,

Commented [DF1]: Should probably be S4 now

Commented [DF2]: Please re number and list in the supplementary in the same order in which they are called out here- put the table after the figure in the SI. I guess this should be S5

$$211 \quad f(x) = ax^2 + bx + c \quad [3]$$

$$212 \quad a = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{2(x_2 - x_1)} \quad [4]$$

$$213 \quad b = m_1 - 2ax_1 \quad [5]$$

$$214 \quad c = y_1 - ax_1^2 - bx_1 \quad [6]$$

215 where x_1 , y_1 and m_1 are the time of deformation initiation, the corresponding voltage and the
 216 drift voltage with time, respectively and the subscript 2 denotes the same terms in the period
 217 after deformation. The final corrected voltage is obtained by subtracting this background
 218 function from the original data. A visual step-by-step example of the drift correction process is
 219 presented in Supplementary Figure S7.

Commented [DF3]: Fig S6

220 2.4 Effect of hydrostatic pressure on d_{11}

221 Hydrostatic pressure may modify the piezoelectric coefficient d_{11} , but measurements of d_{11} as a
 222 function of pressure for CTGS are not currently available. We therefore bound plausible
 223 behavior using structural and theoretical constraints from related oxide piezoelectrics. For
 224 example, density-functional perturbation calculations on rhombohedral BiAlO_3 show a ~35%
 225 increase in the principal piezoelectric coefficient between 0 and 10 GPa, driven by pressure-
 226 induced internal coordinate shifts rather than symmetry changes (Almaghbash & Arbouche,
 227 2021). By contrast, much larger pressure sensitivities reported for α -quartz are associated with
 228 proximity to pressure-dependent structural instabilities (Herzbach & Müser, 2006).

229 High-pressure crystallographic studies of langasite-family crystals show that their trigonal
 230 framework remains elastically stable up to approximately 12 GPa before undergoing a
 231 symmetry-lowering transition, with no evidence of anomalous softening in the low-pressure
 232 regime (Pavlovska et al., 2002). Structural analyses further attribute the piezoelectric response
 233 of langasite-type materials to cation shifts within a comparatively rigid tetrahedral–octahedral
 234 framework (Morikoshi et al., 2003), suggesting that CTGS should exhibit a smooth, perturbative
 235 pressure dependence more similar to structurally stable oxide piezoelectrics than to quartz. In
 236 the absence of a direct calibration, we therefore do not apply a deterministic pressure
 237 correction to d_{11} . Instead, we propagate a conservative $\pm 20\%$ relative uncertainty over our
 238 experimental pressure range to account for plausible pressure sensitivity. This contribution is
 239 included explicitly in the stress uncertainty budget discussed below. Future first-principles
 240 calculations or dedicated high-pressure electromechanical measurements would allow direct
 241 calibration of d_{11} for CTGS and reduce this uncertainty.

242 3 Results

243 3.1 Drift Correction

244 Figure 1 shows representative voltage records from uniaxial extension and compression
 245 experiments on single-crystal MgO conducted under varying pressure-temperature conditions.
 246 The experiments, measured in addition to those shown in Table 1 as part of a different
 247 experimental run, were performed at 5.0 GPa and 600 °C (1A), 2.3 GPa and 1000 °C (1B), 3.0
 248 GPa and 1200 °C (1C), and 5.0 GPa and 600 °C (1D), all at a constant strain rate of $3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ to

249 a total strain of 10%. These experiments differ primarily in temperature and pressure, which are
250 expected to influence both the mechanical response of MgO and the stability of the
251 piezoelectric signal. In particular, higher temperatures reduce the flow stress of MgO, while
252 pressure and thermal conditions also affect electrical leakage and hence instrumental drift
253 behavior. As a result, both the absolute stress levels and the magnitude of the baseline drift
254 differ between experiments, even under otherwise comparable loading conditions.

255 The raw signal displays a smooth background drift that would correspond to hundreds of
256 megapascals of apparent stress over the duration of a typical experiment. Applying the
257 constrained background correction described in Section 3.2 removes this long-term drift while
258 preserving short-timescale variations. The different apparent drift magnitudes observed in the
259 parallel experiments do not necessarily indicate differences in mechanical behavior. The
260 absolute pre-deformation drift is adjusted manually on the charge integrator and is therefore
261 somewhat arbitrary in magnitude and sign because it is operator-controlled; what matters for
262 stress reconstruction is the change in drift between the pre- and post-deformation baselines.
263 Because the pre-deformation baseline is manually adjusted on the charge integrator, the initial
264 drift slope can vary substantially from one experiment to another and does not itself carry
265 physical significance. In this case, the bottom right experiment began with a relatively large
266 negative baseline drift, so the raw voltage decreases during deformation even though
267 compressive loading should increase the piezoelectric signal; by contrast, the bottom left
268 experiment began with a much smaller positive drift and therefore appears to require less
269 correction.

270 After correction, the expected increase in stress with strain is recovered. At equivalent strain,
271 the lower-temperature 600 °C compression experiment (1D) yields the higher stress, whereas
272 the higher-temperature 1200 °C experiment (1C) yields the lower stress, consistent with the
273 greater strength of MgO at lower temperature and its thermal weakening at higher
274 temperature. The correction procedure is constrained entirely by independently measured
275 boundary slopes and introduces no free fitting parameters. As a result, it cannot absorb
276 genuine mechanical signals occurring within the deformation interval. This behavior confirms
277 that the correction acts only on the slowly varying background and does not distort the stress
278 history derived from the piezoelectric signal.

Commented [DF4]: Ok I am very surprised about these conditions being at 5 GPa because in Table 1 and in the methods it says you did experiments up to 3 GPa can you please clarify this. If these are in fact the correct pressures could you make a statement here something along the lines of - these test experiments were performed in addition to those shown in table 1 or add these experiments also to table 1. Also please add the conditions of the experiments to the figure caption of figure 1

Figure 1: Example of four deformation experiments. The raw voltage as measured with the charge integrator as well as the post-correction voltage are shown in the top half of each plot. The bottom half shows the percent shortening or lengthening of the complete assembly, calculated from the relative change in anvil position measured by the position encoders (i.e., the change in encoder position during deformation normalized by the initial position). The vertical dashed gray lines mark the start and end of deformation, respectively. The conditions are as follows, (A) 5.0 GPa and 600 °C; (B) 2.3 GPa and 1000 °C; (C) 3.0 GPa and 1200 °C; (D) 5.0 GPa and 600 °C.

Commented [DF5]: Please also include the conditions of the experiments here- you might also think about labelling them A to D.

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286 **3.2 Precision Estimation**

287 During compression or deformation, the 6-axis multianvil press does not achieve a perfectly
 288 smooth advance of the anvils due to small overshoots in the required oil pressure to achieve a
 289 particular anvil position. This results in small oscillatory positional adjustments that are
 290 recorded by the positional encoders and are of the order of $1\ \mu\text{m}$. This oscillation provides a
 291 good opportunity to examine the sensitivity of the piezoelectric crystal as the integrated
 292 voltage records this behavior as a sawtooth signal. Figure 2 shows a representative time
 293 window after removing the linear deformation trend to highlight this oscillation. In panel (a),
 294 the black trace tracks anvil position and in panel (b), it tracks anvil velocity. The anvil motion
 295 repeats every 48 s. The voltage responds at the same frequency with a 4 s lag. Panel (b) also
 296 shows the corresponding voltage slew rate (dV/dt , in V s^{-1}), defined as the instantaneous rate
 297 of change of the integrator output, which is directly proportional to changes in stress. Plotting
 298 the slew rate accentuates the phase relation, i.e., the anvils move first, and the voltage follows
 299 4 s later. The close match between anvil kinematics and voltage confirms that the sawtooth
 300 voltage pattern reflects this press control cycle.

301

Commented [DF6]: in your original document the two figures both showed a velocity scale but I found the figure that shows the anvil position on the y axis

Commented [ND7R6]: Yeah, I made a mistake there. My goal was to show position and voltage on the top plot (i.e., basically distance space) and velocity and voltage slew rate on the bottom half (i.e., speed space). The reason for this was to show the absolute jiggle amount (i.e., microns) to show the precision of the piezoelectric crystal, and the velocity of the change (bottom figure) to show that the voltage reacts to the change in anvil speed quite quickly.

The initial figure was wrong. This is the corrected one for what I wanted to show. It was an old version that I caught and fixed after I sent it to you.

Figure 2: Anvil-movement oscillation during deformation showing (a) direct voltage and anvil position and (b) voltage slew rate and anvil velocity.

302

303 This periodic response provides an effective in-window probe of measurement precision for the
 304 present assembly. In Figure 3, we isolate the oscillation by fitting a Voigt profile to the Fast
 305 Fourier transform (FFT) magnitude to obtain the peak frequency ($f_0 = 0.020415$ Hz). We then
 306 apply a Butterworth band-pass filter with a width tied to the fitted Voigt full width at half
 307 maximum and demodulate at f_0 to separate the coherent sinusoidal component from the in-
 308 band residual. The direct-voltage residual has a standard deviation of 9.027 mV, which we
 309 convert to stress using Eq. 2. We propagate three independent sources of uncertainty: a 1%
 310 manufacturer tolerance for the integrating capacitor C_F , an 18% relative uncertainty for the
 311 piezoelectric coefficient d_{11} , and a 4% relative uncertainty for the electrode area A arising from
 312 a 2% diameter measurement error. Combined in quadrature, these contributions yield an
 313 18.5% relative uncertainty on Eq. 2. The resulting stress noise level is 1.789 ± 0.330 MPa (one
 314 standard deviation), and the corresponding three-standard-deviation decision threshold is
 315 5.368 ± 0.991 MPa.

316 In Figure 3, the upper panel plots the band-passed voltage expressed in MPa together with the
 317 fitted sinusoid and shaded one- and three-standard-deviation bands referenced to this stress
 318 noise level. The lower panel shows the residual-stress histogram with a normal-density overlay,
 319 indicating approximately Gaussian in-band noise and supporting the quoted precision levels.

Commented [DF8]: Is this the right equation - I suspect not- I think this is Eq. 2????

Figure 3: Precision estimate from in-window press oscillation. Top: band-passed direct voltage converted to stress with fitted sinusoid and $\pm 1\sigma/\pm 3\sigma$ bands. Bottom: residual- stress histogram with normal overlay.

320

321 3.3 Single-crystal deformation

322 Single-crystal deformation experiments target specific slip systems to evaluate shear strength
 323 and dislocation slip-system activity as a function of temperature and pressure. Although the
 324 high-pressure and high-temperature deformation behavior of single-crystal MgO and forsterite

325 has been extensively studied, published datasets still show significant scatter and under
326 comparable conditions. Independent measurements obtained with the in situ piezoelectric
327 stress sensor, therefore, provide valuable constraints for assessing experimental reproducibility
328 and testing the performance of the piezoelectric method. MgO and forsterite were selected as
329 benchmark materials because their deformation behavior is sufficiently well characterized to
330 allow comparison with literature data (Darot & Guéguen, 1981; Demouchy et al., 2009; Mei et
331 al., 2008; Raterron et al., 2007), while still providing meaningful new constraints on stress
332 determination at high pressure.

333 Deformation experiments were performed at pressures between 1.5 and 3 GPa and
334 temperatures of 600-1300°C. Strain was determined from the anvil displacements measured by
335 the encoders. All experiments were conducted at a constant strain rate of $-5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for 3333
336 s (55.5 minutes), corresponding to a total strain of 0.167.

337 Total strain was estimated from the difference between initial and final anvil positions,
338 assuming that the imposed shortening was accommodated primarily within the sample. This
339 assumption neglects elastic and assembly contributions and, therefore, introduces a systematic
340 uncertainty in absolute strain, but it does not affect relative comparisons between experiments.
341 After decompression, recovered crystals were commonly fractured, preventing reliable post-
342 mortem measurement of sample length and confirming that absolute strain cannot be
343 determined independently. Based on comparable large-volume experiments, the encoder-
344 derived strain likely carries a systematic uncertainty of approximately a factor of two.

345 The calculated stress-strain curves for each experiment listed in Table 1 are shown in Figure 4.
346 On a qualitative level these results indicate that forsterite is clearly stronger than MgO. The
347 variation in stress-strain behavior is also consistent with the expected rheology of crystalline
348 solids under high pressure and temperature. Increasing hydrostatic pressure leads to higher
349 flow stress because compression reduces free volume and increases resistance to dislocation
350 motion. In contrast, increasing temperature produces pronounced weakening as thermal
351 activation enhances atomic mobility and lowers the energy barrier for dislocation glide and
352 climb. Figure 4 illustrates these competing effects clearly: both MgO and forsterite exhibit
353 higher flow stresses at 3.0 GPa than at lower pressures, whereas increasing temperature
354 systematically reduces the stress required to sustain deformation at fixed strain rate. The latter
355 effect can also be seen to be stronger for MgO than forsterite.

356 Several experiments display the onset of steady-state creep, (highlighted in bold in Table 1). In
357 these cases, the materials transition from an initial elastic loading regime into a plateau where
358 stress remains approximately constant while strain accumulates. The stress-strain curves in
359 Figure 4 show this behavior clearly: an initial linear segment is followed by a flattening of the
360 curve that marks the onset of plastic flow. Once such steady-state conditions are reached, the
361 measured stress is taken as the flow stress at the imposed strain rate.

362 The temperature dependence of this transition is evident across all pressure conditions. At
363 higher temperatures the plateau stress decreases systematically, confirming that thermal
364 softening dominates the mechanical response within the explored pressure range. The
365 observed trends agree with previously reported deformation data for single-crystal MgO and
366 forsterite, as discussed in the next section, and demonstrate that the piezoelectric stress sensor

367 captures the expected pressure- and temperature-dependent rheology of these benchmark
 368 materials.

Figure 4: Stress-strain plots of deformation experiments performed on synthetic single-crystal MgO and forsterite at pressures and temperatures indicated. Stresses are determined from the piezoelectric crystal. The three plots in the left column are for MgO and the right column of forsterite both aligned with the [100] parallel to the deformation axis. The vertical dashed black line marks the end of deformation. All experiments were conducted at $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ strain rate.

Commented [DF9]: May be give the strain rate

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379 Table 1: Experimental conditions for deformation of forsterite and MgO
 380 single crystals oriented with [100] parallel to the deformation axis.
 381 Experiments in bold went through a σ maximum before the end of
 382 deformation

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Oil Pressure (bar)	Sample Pressure (GPa)	Temperature (°C)	Maximum σ (MPa)
Forsterite single crystal [100]			
15.3	1.5	800	1779
15.3	1.5	1000	1554
15.3	1.5	1200	1280
15.3	1.5	1300	1156
24.1	2.3	600	1960
24.1	2.3	800	1704
24.1	2.3	1000	1531
24.1	2.3	1200	1368
24.1	2.3	1300	1175
33.4	3.0	600	1375
33.4	3.0	800	1545
33.4	3.0	1000	1590
33.4	3.0	1200	1552
33.4	3.0	1300	1343
MgO single crystal [100]			
15.3	1.5	800	750
15.3	1.5	1000	481
15.3	1.5	1200	217
15.3	1.5	1300	99
24.1	2.3	600	1377
24.1	2.3	800	1060
24.1	2.3	1200	578
24.1	2.3	1300	364
33.4	3.0	600	1666
33.4	3.0	800	1449
33.4	3.0	1000	1417
33.4	3.0	1300	409

387

388 4 Discussion

389 The results demonstrate that the piezoelectric stress sensor reproduces, at least qualitatively,
 390 the expected pressure–temperature dependence of plastic flow in well-characterized
 391 benchmark materials. To evaluate the agreement quantitatively, the data must be expressed
 392 within a common creep framework that allows comparison with published experiments
 393 conducted at different pressures, temperatures, and strain rates.

394 To quantify the pressure–temperature–stress (P–T– σ) conditions of creep strength, the
 395 experimental data were fit to the classical power-law creep equation:

$$396 \quad \dot{\epsilon} = A\sigma^n \exp\left(-\frac{E^*+PV^*}{RT}\right) \quad [7]$$

397
 398 where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is strain rate, σ is differential stress, A is a material constant, n is the stress exponent,
 399 E^* is activation energy, V^* is activation volume, P is pressure, R is the gas constant, and T is
 400 temperature.

401 Previous studies have examined single-crystal deformation of MgO and forsterite under
 402 comparable high-pressure conditions using synchrotron-based techniques. Raterron et al.
 403 (2007) measured creep of oriented olivine crystals, $[110]_c$ and $[011]_c$, between 2.1–7.5 GPa and
 404 1373–1677 K in a D-DIA apparatus. Raterron et al. (2009) extended this work to examine
 405 variable oxygen fugacity and water contents. Girard et al. (2013) quantified hydrolytic
 406 weakening in forsterite (oriented $[110]_c$) between 4–7 GPa, while Girard et al. (2012) performed
 407 MgO deformation experiments between 4–9 GPa and 1273–1473 K on single crystals oriented
 408 $[100]_c$, $[110]_c$, and $[111]_c$. In our work, all crystals were oriented $[100]_c$. Although differences in
 409 crystallographic orientation limit direct quantitative comparison of fitted parameters, the
 410 overall agreement in stress–strain behavior with these synchrotron-based datasets provides a
 411 robust validation of the piezoelectric approach as a reliable in situ stress sensor that does not
 412 require the use of in situ synchrotron X-ray measurements.

413 For olivine, Raterron et al. (2007) reported fitted values for A , n , E^* , and V^* . Later studies
 414 provided subsets of these parameters, leaving A to vary. For MgO, Girard et al. (2012) reported
 415 only the stress exponent n ; their data were reanalyzed here using the same fitting framework
 416 employed for the present dataset. Because our experiments use a single imposed strain rate,
 417 allowing n to vary leads to unstable inversions. We therefore fix $n = 3$, consistent with high-
 418 temperature dislocation climb-controlled creep in both MgO and forsterite (Amodeo et al.,
 419 2018; Mei et al., 2008; Wilshire, 1995).

420 The fitted parameters are listed in Table 2. Parameters fixed from prior work are marked
 421 accordingly. These fits allow prediction of stress or strain rate over a broad range of pressure–
 422 temperature conditions as long as dislocation creep remains the dominant mechanism.
 423 Forsterite results are compared in Figure 5 and MgO in Figure 6. Our curves fall within the
 424 uncertainty envelopes of previously published creep laws and in several cases reduce the
 425 spread of allowable stress predictions.

426 The principal discrepancy arises in the MgO activation volume. Our best-fit value of $V^*=24.6$
 427 produces a stronger pressure dependence than the near-zero activation volumes inferred by
 428 Girard et al. (2012). Because our experiments span pressures only up to 3 GPa, whereas their
 429 dataset extends to 9 GPa, their higher-pressure results may constrain activation volume more
 430 robustly. This mismatch highlights a well-known tradeoff in creep inversions: the pre-
 431 exponential factor A can compensate for changes in activation volume, and E^* and V^* may trade
 432 off against each other. Power-law creep fitting is inherently unstable when applied to limited
 433 datasets, and multiple local minima may exist in parameter space.

Commented [DF10]: Please check the numbering of all equations is consistent

Commented [DF11]: Could you mention something here about the orientations of the crystals examined- and may be include a statement that recognises that you don't have measurements on exactly the same aligned crystal.

Commented [ND12R11]: Ok, done.

434 To mitigate this instability, we minimize the misfit function

435

$$436 \quad \Phi(\mathbf{m}) = \sum_i [\ln \sigma_{model}(\dot{\epsilon}_i, T_i, P_i; \mathbf{m}) - \ln \sigma_i]^2 \quad [8]$$

437

438 using a differential-evolution global search followed by Monte Carlo refits of perturbed
 439 synthetic datasets. This approach reduces sensitivity to local minima and produces stable
 440 uncertainty estimates for all parameters. The resulting creep parameters therefore represent
 441 statistically consistent solutions within the limits imposed by the pressure range of the
 442 experiments.

443 The creep-law comparison, therefore, indicates that the piezoelectric measurements recover
 444 stress magnitudes and trends that are mainly consistent with the best available synchrotron-
 445 based datasets. The remaining discrepancies fall within expected inversion tradeoffs and reflect
 446 dataset size rather than systematic sensor bias.

447

Figure 5: Comparison of power-law creep stress for forsterite (Mg_2SiO_4). On the left stress is plotted as a function of pressure (GPa) at 1300 K, and on the right stress is plotted as a function of temperature (K) at 3 GPa. Black curves show results from this study, blue and green curves indicate data from Raterron et al. (2007). Red and yellow are results from Raterron et al. (2009). Shaded regions, matching the color of each curve, indicate the respective error ranges.

448

449

Figure 6: Comparison of power-law creep stress for MgO. On the left stress is plotted as a function of pressure (GPa) at 1300 K, and on the right stress is plotted as a function of temperature (K) at 3 GPa. Black curves indicate results from this study. Green, blue, and red curves are from Girard et al. (2012). Shaded regions, matching the color of each curve, indicate the respective error ranges.

450

451 5 Conclusions

452 We developed and validated a piezoelectric method for measuring deviatoric stress in a cubic
 453 large-volume press without synchrotron diffraction. Embedding a CTGS crystal in the
 454 deformation column and coupling it to a precision charge integrator provides continuous in situ
 455 stress histories during single-crystal deformation of MgO and forsterite at pressures up to 3 GPa
 456 and temperatures up to 1400 °C.

457 The assembly architecture thermally isolates the sensor while maintaining mechanical
 458 representativeness. A diamond heat sink and insulating sleeve keep the crystal below ~200 °C
 459 even when the sample exceeds 1200 °C. Power–temperature calibration confirms a stable
 460 thermal gradient and ensures operation in a regime where electrical leakage remains controlled
 461 and the piezoelectric response is linear.

462 We characterized integrator drift over nearly eight orders of magnitude in resistance and
 463 implemented a constrained parabolic correction scheme that removes leakage while preserving
 464 mechanical signals. Analysis of periodic ram oscillations provides an internal precision
 465 benchmark, yielding a stress noise level of a few megapascals and a conservative detection
 466 threshold near 5 MPa. After propagating uncertainties in capacitance, electrode geometry, and
 467 piezoelectric response, total stress uncertainty remains below ~20%.

468 Deformation experiments on MgO and forsterite produce stress–strain behavior consistent
 469 with established single-crystal creep laws. The fitted activation parameters fall within the
 470 published range and reproduce expected pressure–temperature trends. Agreement with

471 synchrotron-based datasets demonstrates that the CTGS assembly recovers reliable differential
472 stresses without requiring in situ X-ray methods.

473 This capability enables high-throughput deformation studies in laboratory-based presses
474 without synchrotron beamtime constraints. Future work should be aimed at determining
475 whether there is an effect of pressure on the CTGS piezoelectric coefficient. This could be
476 examined using ab initio calculations. Furthermore, experiments combining piezoelectric
477 sensing with in situ X-ray diffraction could be used to provide cross calibration of the method at
478 higher pressures. In situ radiography could also be used to examine the extent of strain
479 partitioning within the deformation column of the assembly.

480

481

482

483

484 Table 2: Creep parameters for single crystal forsterite and MgO. A
485 superscript f denotes a parameter that is fixed during fitting.
486

Source	σ_1 direction	A ($\text{s}^{-1} \text{Pa}^{-n}$)	n	E^* (kJ/mol)	V^* (cm^3/mol)
<i>Single crystal forsterite</i>					
This study	[100] _c	1.9×10^{-29} $\pm 2.0 \times 10^{-30}$	3^f	67 ± 24	6.5 ± 4.5
Raterron et al. (2007)	[110] _c	1.5×10^{-29f} $\pm 8.4 \times 10^{-25}$	2.6 ± 0.3^f	112 ± 40^f	3.0 ± 0.5^f
Raterron et al. (2007)	[011] _c	4.0×10^{-26f} $\pm 6.2 \times 10^{-27}$	2.7 ± 0.3^f	104 ± 40^f	1.0 ± 0.5^f
Raterron et al. (2009)	[110] _c	1.5×10^{-24} $\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-24}$	3.5 ± 0.1^f	250 ± 50^f	12 ± 4^f
Raterron et al. (2009)	[011] _c	2.3×10^{-26} $\pm 6.2 \times 10^{-27}$	3.5 ± 0.1^f	250 ± 50^f	3 ± 4^f
Girard et al. (2013)	[110] _c	1.5×10^{-15} $\pm 5.4 \times 10^{-16}$	3.5 ± 0.7^f	470 ± 61^f	15.6 ± 2.0^f
<i>Single crystal MgO</i>					
This study	[100] _c	4.8×10^{-26} $\pm 2.2 \times 10^{-27}$	3^f	76 ± 10	24.6 ± 5.0
Girard et al. (2012)	[100] _c	4.5×10^{-23} $\pm 2.3 \times 10^{-23}$	3^f	204 ± 87	1.0 ± 0.5^f
Girard et al. (2012)	[110] _c	1.8×10^{-20} $\pm 6.5 \times 10^{-21}$	3^f	279 ± 78	0.0 ± 0.5^f
Girard et al. (2012)	[111] _c	8.8×10^{-19} $\pm 5.8 \times 10^{-19}$	3^f	328 ± 82	0.0 ± 0.5^f

487

488

489

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496

497 **Open Research**

498 Data is available at:

499 Dolinschi, J. and D. Frost. Deformation Data on Single Crystal MgO and Forsterite. Zenodo, 5 May 2026,
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501 **Conflict of Interest Disclosure**

502 The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest for this manuscript.

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